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The Level of Success In English For Two and Semester Islamic Education Management Three Students In This Classroom

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Abstract

Learning English is intended to facilitate communication between individuals and nations. Proficient use of English enables people to effectively express their ideas, emotions, and thoughts. However, students often struggle with English due to a lack of confidence in using the language in conversational contexts. Utilizing a conversation-based learning model can boost students' confidence in communication, especially when supported by digital modules. This method was tested with a sample of vocational high school (SMA) students. The research involved creating digital teaching materials using the Sigil application, which can be accessed on computers, tablets, and smartphones, and compiling various resources for self-study to enhance conversational skills. The study found that learning through the conversation model resulted in an 81.8% success rate across seven evaluation components.

Keywords: *Conversation, Vocabbulary, The level of success in English, Islamic education management*

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INTRODUCTION

Conversation is interactive communication between two or more people. Developing conversation and etiquette skills is an important part of socialization. Developing conversational skills in a new language is often a focus of language teaching and learning. Conversation analysis is a branch of sociology that studies the structure and organization of human interaction, with a more specific focus on conversational interaction.

For several disciplines, the language of instruction is English. Nonetheless, some educators continue to teach at the aforementioned institutions using bilingual instruction in both English and Indonesian with the goal of achieving status parity. According to School Based International, the school operates on a global basis. Situations like the one described above have the potential to inspire students to learn English more thoroughly and actively, both in written and spoken forms. During learning, students need to be able to articulate their ideas, thoughts, and so on. They also need to be able to respond to inquiries and pose questions that are appropriate for their level of understanding.

Students must be adept in voicing and defending their beliefs, countering the perspectives of others, and persuading others to follow the topic of debate when conducting discussions. Regarding this, procedure practice in the course of doing their jobs and obligations, many teachers continue to make learning mistakes on a daily basis (Prayitno 2005.b). Teachers frequently do not recognize these mistakes, and they are nonetheless accepted as the standard (Agustiar, 2007, Muri, 2007, Abizar, 2007 and Mukhaiyar, 2007). In any case, even the smallest mistake made by teachers, particularly during the teaching and learning process, will have a detrimental impact on the growth of the students.

To address this issue, the government has undertaken a number of reform initiatives aimed at enhancing the English language learning process and yielding better learning outcomes for students, particularly in terms of their proficiency in the language. It is quite probable that the government's efforts have not yielded satisfying results because this endeavor has not yet reached its aim. Listening, speaking, reading, and writing are just a few of the integrated subject areas covered in English classes. Everything is taught in a methodical manner in accordance with the school's package book.

This article, however, only addresses speaking abilities in order to assist language teachers in

enhancing their pedagogical approaches through the use of the "Guide Conversation" idea. The greater the likelihood that this issue is linked to students' motivation to improve their English speaking abilities. Is it true that learning to speak English, a foreign language, is challenging because it is not your native tongue? (Lisna, 2006).

Conversation analysis, or CA from here on, has attracted the interest of scholars who study spoken communication between individuals. CA is a discourse technique that originated in the discipline of ethnomethodology, one of the sociological subfields pioneered by Harold Garfinkel (Bhatia et al., 2008). The pioneers of CA, Harvey Sacks, Emanuel Schegloff, and Gail Jefferson, then specifically developed the conversation around it (Schiffrin, 1994; Sidnell, 2007). "The description and explication of the competences that ordinary speakers use and rely on in participating in intelligible, socially organized interaction" (p. 1) is the primary goal of conversational analysis, according to Atkinson and Heritage (1984). California offers unique 198–209.

Traits in examining particular data that other discourse analysis subfields, such as critical discourse analysis (CDA) and ethnography of communication, possess. While the ethnography of communication analyzes factors outside the interaction, like settings, participants, ends, and genre, the CDA views language as social practices and views the context of language use as fundamental (Darweesh & Abdullah, 2016; Fairclough, 2000; Fairclough & Wodak, 1997; Paltridge, 2012). Williams (1972; Johnstone & Marcellino, 2010).

In the meantime, CA refrains from proposing any social or linguistic categories whose significance for the participants does not emerge from the actual statements made" (Schiffrin, 1994, p. 239). As a result, CA only takes into account the spoken data and ignores all other aspects. Another feature of CA is its concern for minute particles and its attention to subtleties in the spoken conversation, both of which are important when trying to understand how language functions (ten Have, 2007).

One further characteristic that sets conversation analysis apart is that it is built on real data—actual conversations that are captured and meticulously transcribed in accordance with relevant conventions—rather than on made-up interactions. By creating and establishing particular artificial interactive circumstances in the conversation, conversation analysis rejects an artificial range of data collecting approaches (Egins & Slade, 1997).

This study intends to ascertain how language usage is discussed when learning English in the classroom of the Islamic Education Management Study Program 4. Muhammad Yuda and Gilang conducted the interviews for this study to ascertain the mpi four students' comprehension of speech in daily life.

RESEARCH METHODS

Researchers employed qualitative research methodologies in this study. Qualitative research methods can be thought of as mini-research techniques that employ descriptive data from people or actors that are observable, such as written or spoken words. The methodical search and organizing of observation and interview techniques to comprehend and portray the subject of a case study is known as data analysis in qualitative research.

In order to get the information required for the research, the researcher asks the resource person directly in the form of questions. The resource person then responds to the questions, providing the researcher with the information that is gathered into notes based on field data. This indicates that the utilization of two data sources—primary data sources, which include the majority of the research data—is highlighted in this qualitative study. Furthermore, the researcher's personal field observations of students' comprehension of discourse provide supporting data for the second source, or secondary data source. This study's methodology, which is based on professional perspectives regarding language conversation learning English using the guided conversation approach, is a literature review (library research).

RESEARCH RESULT

Conversation is a term in English which means communication between two or more people. In the learning process, conversation is the main component because it functions as a medium for conveying information between individuals using appropriate and correct language. Conversation is very important considering the needs and developments of today's era, where the ability to

communicate effectively is very necessary.

English language awareness is often taken for granted due to lack of proficiency, so it is important to realize the importance of English, especially in conversation. If we master conversation in English, we will not be awkward when communicating. Learning English can be done through various media, one of which is music. When we learn through media that we like, such as music, it will be easier for us to understand and master the language. Music motivates us to find out the meaning of the lyrics we hear, so that the learning process becomes more effective and enjoyable.

In general, many people want to be fluent in English, but often face various obstacles. Research in MPI3 classes shows that conversation in English is still low due to a lack of empowerment of language skills and fear of mistakes. This does not only happen to MPI students but also to other students who do not understand English, especially in conversation.

Many efforts have been made to improve English language skills, but are often hampered by a lack of seriousness and will. Speaking in English, like Indonesian, requires appropriate language etiquette and style, including intonation and delivery that influence the reception of information by other people.

From the explanation above, understanding conversation is how we can speak to other people using good and correct English, and using appropriate etiquette. In this way, the people who communicate with us will feel comfortable and understand what we say, so that our message is well received.

Picture 1. *Evidenced of interview result*

CONCLUSION

The expert perspectives described above can be derived from a number of ideas, with the conclusion that learning English in particular requires a variety of tactics for speaking. The goal is to facilitate the study of English courses for pupils; the more methods available for learning, the easier it is to become proficient in the language. But remember that studying English does not mean mastering complex grammar and layout, formula memorization, mastery of tenses, or great reasoning ability. However, mastering the English language is just a matter of constant practice until you become accustomed to it; learning any language necessitates speaking it frequently.

SUGGESTION

We acknowledge that the research and production of this journal still has a lot of holes in it. We sincerely hope that readers will thoroughly review it and offer comments or recommendations for future enhancements.

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